

RESEARCH ON THE MANUFACTURING OF MEN'S SHIRTS USING THE GARMENT DYEING METHOD

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Abstract. *This article explores the garment dyeing method in the sewing industry and its growing demand, analyzes the assortment of men's summer casual clothing, and compares traditional and garment dyeing production methods of men's shirts. The differences, advantages, and limitations of each approach are evaluated.*

Keywords: *textile, cotton, fiber, casual clothes, fabric, garment dyeing.*

INTRODUCTION

In our country, the textile, knitwear, and garment industries are among the most strategically important and rapidly developing sectors of the national economy. The favorable conditions created by the government for industrial enterprises, relevant legislation, and the implementation of presidential decrees and resolutions have significantly contributed to the sector's development. Accordingly, manufacturing companies are expected to produce high-quality, competitive, and innovative products.

It is known that the majority of fibers produced in Uzbekistan are cotton-based, and in recent years, substantial achievements have been made in deep processing. Many textile enterprises have been established, offering dozens of colors of cotton fabrics in plain, twill, and satin weaves. These fabrics are used to produce high-quality clothing for both domestic markets and export.

Garment Dyeing Method and Its Demand in the Apparel Industry

Modern market conditions and fierce competition necessitate fast adaptation. Recently, garment manufacturers have been compelled to deliver fashionable, casual clothing in trending colors within tight deadlines. In conventional textile production cycles, processes such as dyeing, finishing, and delivery are time-consuming, potentially leading to lost sales [1–3]. Garment dyeing enables rapid response to market needs and modern fashion trends.

Figure 1. *Main stages in the production of a men's shirts using the garment dyeing method a) undyed cotton fabric, b) garment sewn from this fabric, c) final appearance after the dyeing process.*

The garment dyeing method enables manufacturers to meet diverse color preferences and market trends within short timeframes. It allows direct dyeing of sewn or partially sewn garments, offering several advantages [4–5]:

- Lower production costs;
- Shorter order fulfillment timelines;
- Increased responsiveness to market changes;
- Reduced inventory buildup;
- Combined washing, bleaching, and dyeing in one machine;
- Fast adaptation to fashion trends;
- Minimal dyeing equipment required;
- Creation of special effects (e.g., faded, vintage, scratched, glossy looks);
- Possibility of re-dyeing faded garments.

However, this method has limitations, such as fabric deformation during dyeing, incompatibility with some synthetic or blended fibers, limited colorfastness, and other technical constraints. A key issue is dimensional shrinkage of cotton fabrics during dyeing, especially in the warp and weft directions. Thus, pre-determining shrinkage levels is critical during the design process.

Comparative Analysis of Traditional and Garment Dyeing Methods in Men’s Shirt Production.

Domestic garment factories produce a wide range of men’s summer casual wear using cotton fabrics, primarily sourced from local textile enterprises. Summer garments can be categorized into two types: knitted and woven fabric-based. (Table 1).

Table 1. Assortment of Men’s Casual Summer Clothing

Knitwear	Woven garments
T-shirts	Half placket shirts
Polo shirts	Dress shirts
Shorts	Trousers
Pants	Shorts
Sets	Sets
Jackets and etc.	Jackets and etc.

Fabrics used for these garments may be 100% cotton, cotton-polyester blends, or other synthetic mixes. They may be solid-dyed, striped, checkered, or printed. Dyeing can occur at the fiber/yarn stage, after weaving, or post-garment assembly. While fabric dyeing is a time-tested technique, garment dyeing emerged in the 1970s–80s and currently accounts for about 20% of global casual garment production [3–6].

Figure 2.7 presents the process stages of manufacturing a men's shirt from cotton fabric using both the traditional and garment dyeing methods, along with the average delivery time of the finished product to the retailer (or customer).

As shown in Figure 2, traditional methods take 2–4 times longer than garment dyeing. Since seasonal garments must be produced 1–2 months in advance, misalignment with real-time market demand may lead to forecasting errors and sales risks.

Figure 2. Comparative timelines for producing men’s shirts using traditional and garment dyeing methods

In the traditional method, the garment factory pre-orders fabric with specific color and density from the textile supplier. Based on studies of major Uzbek textile companies, fabric production and delivery may range from 2 weeks to several months.

Table 2. Dyed Fabric Delivery Times of Major Uzbek Textile Companies

Textile Company	Delivery Time
Posco International Textile (Fergana)	2–6 weeks
Deluxe Fabric (Bukhara)	4–6 weeks
Merganteks (Bukhara)	4–6 weeks
Samarkand Euro Asia Textile	8–24 weeks
Osiyo Home Tex (Namangan)	2–4 weeks
Real Tex Tashkent	6–8 weeks
Marjon Textile	4–6 weeks

As seen in Table 2, the main delay in producing men’s shirts from cotton-based woven fabrics is due to the time required to prepare the fabric. While this is the primary drawback of the traditional method, its key advantage lies in the ability to mass-produce a single type of garment more quickly [9]. The advantage of the garment dyeing method is the flexibility to postpone color selection until the final stage of production, allowing better alignment with changing market demands. However, its main drawback is the limitation in dyeing garments to anything other than solid (piece-dyed) colors—except through certain specialized techniques.

CONCLUSION

The garment dyeing method, a distinctive approach in the apparel manufacturing industry, was analyzed along with the reasons behind its demand and its advantages over the traditional method.

The production of men's shirts from cotton fabric using both the traditional and garment dyeing methods was examined, highlighting the differences and respective process stages.

An analysis of several major textile enterprises in Uzbekistan revealed that the production and delivery times of finished fabrics to garment factories vary, with the primary delay in cotton fabric-based garment production attributed to the fabric preparation stage.

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